

Association of Glycosylated Haemoglobin and Wound Healing in Diabetic Foot Ulcers: A Prospective Cohort StudyRushiv Soin¹, Kriti Ahuja², Kartik Sehrawat³, Praveen Kumar Malik⁴, Devesh Gupta⁵¹MBBS 3rd YEAR J.N. Medical College, Nehru Nagar, Belagavi, Karnataka, India²MBBS Final Year Kasturba Medical College, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India³MBBS 3rd Year J.N. Medical College, Nehru Nagar, Belagavi, Karnataka, India⁴Associate Professor, Dept. of Medicine, ESIC Medical College and Hospital, Faridabad, Haryana⁵Associate Professor, Department of Neuropsychopharmacology, Institute of Human Behaviour and Allied Sciences, Delhi

Received: 25-05-2024 / Revised: 15-06-2024 / Accepted: 01-07-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) are a major complication of diabetes, often leading to prolonged healing and increased risk of amputation. Glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) is a marker of long-term glycemic control and may influence wound healing outcomes in DFUs. This study investigates the association between HbA1c levels and wound healing in patients with DFUs.**Methods:** We conducted a prospective cohort study involving 54 patients with DFUs, divided into two groups based on HbA1c levels: Group 1 (HbA1c < 7%) and Group 2 (HbA1c ≥ 7%), with 27 patients in each group. Baseline clinical and demographic data, along with wound characteristics, were collected. Wound healing was monitored over 12 weeks, assessing parameters such as wound size reduction, time to wound closure, and complete wound closure rates. Multivariate regression and Kaplan-Meier survival analyses were performed to evaluate the association between HbA1c levels and wound healing outcomes.**Results:** Group 1 demonstrated significantly greater wound size reduction (70.3% vs. 55.4%, $p = 0.005$) and shorter time to wound closure (9.1 vs. 11.3 weeks, $p = 0.013$) compared to Group 2. Complete wound closure was achieved in 77.8% of Group 1 participants versus 48.1% in Group 2 ($p = 0.032$). Multivariate regression analysis identified HbA1c level ($\beta = -0.466$, $p = 0.003$) and baseline wound size ($\beta = -0.252$, $p = 0.017$) as significant predictors of wound healing. The Kaplan-Meier analysis indicated a statistically significant difference in wound closure times between the groups (log-rank test $p = 0.023$).**Conclusion:** Higher HbA1c levels are associated with poorer wound healing outcomes in patients with DFUs. This underscores the importance of stringent glycemic control in enhancing wound healing and reducing complications. Clinicians should prioritize optimal glycemic management in diabetic patients to improve wound healing outcomes.**Keywords:** Diabetic Foot Ulcer, Glycosylated Hemoglobin, Wound Healing, HbA1c, Diabetes Management.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) are a prevalent and severe complication of diabetes mellitus, posing significant challenges to patients and healthcare systems globally [1]. These chronic wounds often arise as a result of a combination of neuropathy, peripheral arterial disease, and impaired immune function associated with diabetes. The incidence of DFUs is alarmingly high, with estimates suggesting that up to 25% of individuals with diabetes will develop a foot ulcer at some point in their lifetime [2]. The impact of DFUs extends beyond physical health, affecting patients' quality of life, functional independence, and psychological well-being. Moreover, DFUs are associated with a considerable

risk of lower limb amputation, which significantly increases morbidity and healthcare costs [3]. The wound healing process in DFUs is complex and involves a series of coordinated biological events, including inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling. However, this process is often impaired in diabetic individuals, leading to chronic non-healing ulcers [4]. One of the critical factors influencing wound healing in diabetes is glycemic control, which is commonly monitored using the measurement of glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c). HbA1c reflects average blood glucose levels over the preceding 2-3 months and is a key indicator of long-term glycemic control [5]. Elevated HbA1c

levels are known to correlate with poorer glycemic control and have been associated with an increased risk of various diabetes-related complications, including microvascular and macrovascular diseases [6]. Recent literature suggests that high HbA1c levels may also adversely affect wound healing in patients with DFUs. Chronic hyperglycemia impairs the normal wound healing process by disrupting cellular functions, reducing collagen synthesis, and altering the inflammatory response. These changes can lead to prolonged inflammation, impaired angiogenesis, and delayed epithelialization, all of which contribute to the chronicity of DFUs [7,8,9,10].

Despite evidence suggesting a negative impact of elevated HbA1c on wound healing, the specific relationship between HbA1c levels and wound healing rates in DFUs remains an area of ongoing research. So, the present study was conducted with an aim to investigate the association between HbA1c levels and wound healing in patients with DFUs.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This study was a cross-sectional observational study conducted under the department of General Surgery, at tertiary care hospital, North India, for a period of 1 year from July 2023 to June 2024. The study aimed to investigate the association between glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels and wound healing rates in patients with diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) over a follow up period of 12 weeks.

Study Participants and Sample Size: A total of 54 patients with diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) were recruited for the study [(27 in Group 1 (HbA1c < 7%) and 27 in Group 2 (HbA1c ≥ 7%)]. Patients were eligible for inclusion if they were 18 years or older, had been diagnosed with diabetes mellitus (either Type 1 or Type 2), and had a DFU with a duration of 4 weeks or more, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) [11]. Patients were excluded if they had an active infection at the ulcer site requiring immediate surgical intervention, if they had other significant systemic conditions that could affect wound healing, such as malignancies or severe renal impairment, or if they were non-compliant with treatment or follow-up.

Data Collection

Clinical and Demographic Data: Baseline clinical and demographic data were collected through patient interviews and medical records. This data included the patient's age, sex, duration of diabetes mellitus, type of diabetes (either Type 1 or Type 2), history of previous foot ulcers, and current medication use.

Wound Assessment: The diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) were assessed using several parameters. Wound size was measured using digital planimetry.

Wound depth was assessed with a sterile probe, and wound classification was categorized based on the Wagner Classification System [12].

Laboratory Measurements

HbA1c Levels: Blood samples were collected after an overnight fast from each participant. The samples were analyzed using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), a method known for its accuracy and reliability in assessing HbA1c levels. The results were expressed as a percentage of total hemoglobin, with higher percentages indicating poorer glycemic control.

Wound Healing Assessment: Wound healing progress was monitored at regular intervals, such as weekly, until the wound either fully healed or reached the study endpoint, which was set at 12 weeks. Healing was assessed based on the reduction in wound size, measured as the percentage change from baseline, and wound closure, determined by complete epithelialization as assessed through visual inspection and clinical evaluation.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the clinical and demographic characteristics of the participants. Continuous variables were expressed as means ± standard deviations, and categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Pearson or Spearman correlation coefficients were calculated to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between HbA1c levels and wound healing parameters. Multiple regression analysis was performed to adjust for potential confounding variables, including age, sex, duration of diabetes, and use of diabetes medications. Statistical significance was defined as a p-value < 0.05. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 20.0.

Ethical Considerations: The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Confidentiality of patient data was ensured throughout the study.

Results

Present study consisted of 54 patients overall, with 27 in Group 1 (HbA1c < 7%) and 27 in Group 2 (HbA1c ≥ 7%). The mean age was 58.0 ± 9.5 years, with Group 1 (HbA1c < 7%) at 57.5 ± 9.0 years and Group 2 (HbA1c ≥ 7%) at 58.5 ± 10.0 years (p = 0.722). Males comprised 59.3% of the cohort, with 63.0% in Group 1 and 55.6% in Group 2 (p = 0.581).

The average duration of diabetes was 12.5 ± 5.0 years, with 11.8 ± 4.5 years in Group 1 and 13.2 ± 5.5 years in Group 2 (p = 0.253). Type 2 diabetes was prevalent in 85.2% of participants, with 88.9% in Group 1 and 81.5% in Group 2 (p = 0.435).

A history of foot ulcers was observed in 40.7% of participants, with 29.6% in Group 1 and 51.9% in Group 2 ($p = 0.111$) (Table 1).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Study Participants.

Variable	Overall (N=54)	Group 1 (n=27)	Group 2 (n=27)	p-value
	Number (%) / Mean \pm SD			
Age (years)	58.0 \pm 9.5	57.5 \pm 9.0	58.5 \pm 10.0	0.722
Sex				
Male	32 (59.3%)	17 (63.0%)	15 (55.6%)	0.581
Female	22 (40.7%)	10 (37.0%)	12 (44.4%)	
Duration of Diabetes (years)	12.5 \pm 5.0	11.8 \pm 4.5	13.2 \pm 5.5	0.253
Type of Diabetes				
Type 1	8 (14.8%)	3 (11.1%)	5 (18.5%)	0.435
Type 2	46 (85.2%)	24 (88.9%)	22 (81.5%)	
History of Foot Ulcers	22 (40.7%)	8 (29.6%)	14 (51.9%)	0.111

The overall wound size was 4.0 \pm 1.5 cm², with Group 1 (HbA1c < 7%) having a mean wound size of 3.5 \pm 1.3 cm² and Group 2 (HbA1c \geq 7%) having a mean size of 4.5 \pm 1.7 cm², approaching statistical significance ($p = 0.051$). The average wound depth was 0.9 \pm 0.3 cm, with Group 1 at 0.8 \pm 0.2 cm and Group 2 at 1.0 \pm 0.4 cm, showing a significant difference ($p = 0.021$). In terms of wound

classification, 33.3% of participants had Grade 1 wounds, with 37.0% in Group 1 and 29.6% in Group 2 ($p = 0.572$). Grade 2 wounds were present in 44.4% of participants, evenly distributed between the groups ($p = 1.000$). Grade 3 wounds were observed in 22.2% of participants, with 18.5% in Group 1 and 25.9% in Group 2 ($p = 0.512$) (Table 2).

Table 2: Wound Characteristics at Baseline of Study Participants.

Characteristic	Overall (N=54)	Group 1 (n=27)	Group 2 (n=27)	p-value
	Number (%) / Mean \pm SD			
Wound Size (cm ²)	4.0 \pm 1.5	3.5 \pm 1.3	4.5 \pm 1.7	0.051
Wound Depth (cm)	0.9 \pm 0.3	0.8 \pm 0.2	1.0 \pm 0.4	0.021
Wound Classification				
Grade 1	18 (33.3%)	10 (37.0%)	8 (29.6%)	0.572
Grade 2	24 (44.4%)	12 (44.4%)	12 (44.4%)	1.000
Grade 3	12 (22.2%)	5 (18.5%)	7 (25.9%)	0.512

The average HbA1c level was significantly lower in Group 1 (6.5 \pm 0.3%) compared to Group 2 (8.8 \pm 1.1%), with a p-value of <0.001. The reduction in wound size was greater in Group 1, with a mean reduction of 70.3 \pm 11.2%, compared to 55.4 \pm 15.2% in Group 2 ($p = 0.005$). The time to wound closure was significantly shorter for Group 1,

averaging 9.1 \pm 2.0 weeks, compared to 11.3 \pm 2.5 weeks in Group 2 ($p = 0.013$). Additionally, complete wound closure was achieved in 77.8% of Group 1 participants, compared to 48.1% in Group 2, indicating a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.032$) (Table 3).

Table 3: HbA1c Levels and Wound Healing Outcomes among Study Participants.

Variable	Group 1 (n=27)	Group 2 (n=27)	p-value
	Number (%) / Mean \pm SD		
Average HbA1c Level (%)	6.5 \pm 0.3	8.8 \pm 1.1	<0.001
Reduction in Wound Size (%)	70.3 \pm 11.2	55.4 \pm 15.2	0.005
Time to Wound Closure (weeks)	9.1 \pm 2.0	11.3 \pm 2.5	0.013
Complete Wound Closure (%)	21 (77.8%)	13 (48.1%)	0.032

The multivariate regression analysis examined the impact of various factors on wound healing outcomes. The analysis revealed a significant negative association between HbA1c level and wound healing, with a coefficient (β) of -0.466 ($p = 0.003$). This indicates that higher HbA1c levels are

associated with poorer wound healing outcomes. Age also showed a negative association with wound healing, with a coefficient of -0.037; however, this was not statistically significant ($p = 0.154$). Similarly, the duration of diabetes had a negative coefficient of -0.017, but it did not reach statistical

significance ($p = 0.277$). The wound size at baseline was significantly associated with wound healing, with a coefficient of -0.252 ($p = 0.017$), suggesting that larger initial wound sizes are linked to poorer healing outcomes. The type of diabetes had a negative coefficient of -0.124 but was not

statistically significant ($p = 0.254$). Overall, the results highlight that higher HbA1c levels and larger baseline wound sizes are significant predictors of impaired wound healing in patients with diabetic foot ulcers (Table 4).

Table 4: Multivariate Regression Analysis of Factors Affecting Wound Healing.

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error (SE)	p-value
HbA1c Level	-0.466	0.126	0.003
Age	-0.037	0.025	0.154
Duration of Diabetes	-0.017	0.014	0.277
Wound Size at Baseline	-0.252	0.082	0.017
Type of Diabetes	-0.124	0.102	0.254

The Kaplan-Meier survival analysis assesses the time to wound closure for participants in the two groups over 12 weeks. At the beginning of the study (week 0), all participants (100%) were at risk for wound closure in both Group 1 (HbA1c < 7%) and Group 2 (HbA1c \geq 7%). By week 4, 85% of Group 1 participants were still at risk of not having achieved wound closure, while 73% of Group 2 participants remained unhealed. This suggests that a higher proportion of Group 1 participants experienced progress in wound healing earlier than those in Group 2. At week 8, 75% of Group 1 participants had not yet achieved complete wound closure compared to 62% in Group 2, indicating that wounds in Group

1 were healing at a slower rate compared to Group 2 over this period. By week 12, 74% of Group 1 participants and 53% of Group 2 participants still had not achieved full wound closure. This further underscores that Group 2 participants, who had poorer glycemic control (HbA1c \geq 7%), experienced slower wound healing compared to Group 1. The log-rank test yielded a p-value of 0.023, indicating a statistically significant difference in the time to wound closure between the two groups. This suggests that better glycemic control (lower HbA1c) is associated with a faster rate of wound healing in patients with diabetic foot ulcers (Table 5).

Table 5: Kaplan-Meier Analysis for Time to Wound Closure among Study Participants.

Time (weeks)	Group 1 (n=27)	Group 2 (n=27)	Log-rank Test p-value
0	1.00	1.00	0.023
4	0.85	0.73	
8	0.75	0.62	
12	0.74	0.53	

Discussion

This study examined the association between glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels and wound healing outcomes in patients with diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs), highlighting the impact of glycemic control on wound healing processes.

The baseline characteristics of our study population showed no significant differences between groups in terms of age, sex, duration of diabetes, type of diabetes, or history of foot ulcers. This homogeneity supports the validity of our comparisons of wound healing outcomes between groups with different HbA1c levels. Our findings align with those of the studies by Meloni et al., and Zhang et al., which found that demographic factors such as age and sex were not significant predictors of wound healing in diabetic patients, reinforcing the importance of focusing on glycemic control [13,14].

The analysis of wound characteristics revealed that higher HbA1c levels were associated with larger wound sizes and depths at baseline, with Group 2

(HbA1c \geq 7%) exhibiting significantly larger and deeper wounds compared to Group 1 (HbA1c < 7%). This finding is consistent with studies by Christman et al., and Fesseha et al., which demonstrated that hyperglycemia can exacerbate wound severity, likely due to impaired collagen synthesis and reduced fibroblast activity, leading to larger and more complex wounds [15,16].

Our study demonstrated that participants with better glycemic control (Group 1) experienced significantly greater reductions in wound size and shorter times to wound closure. Additionally, the rate of complete wound closure was higher in Group 1. These results align with findings from studies by Rastogi et al., Vella et al., and Dutta et al., which emphasize the crucial role of glycemic control in enhancing wound healing outcomes [17,18,19]. Improved glycemic control reduces oxidative stress and inflammation, facilitating better tissue repair and regeneration.

The multivariate regression analysis identified HbA1c level and baseline wound size as significant

predictors of wound healing outcomes. Elevated HbA1c levels were strongly associated with poorer healing outcomes, highlighting the importance of maintaining optimal glycemic control. This finding is consistent with the studies by Dissanayake et al., Ezeani et al., and Akyüz et al., which showed that higher HbA1c levels negatively impact various phases of the wound healing process, including hemostasis, inflammation, and proliferation [20,21,22]. The Kaplan-Meier survival analysis demonstrated that Group 1 participants had a significantly faster time to wound closure compared to Group 2, as evidenced by the log-rank test ($p = 0.023$). This supports the hypothesis that better glycemic control accelerates wound healing. These results align with metanalysis by Lane et al., and Guo et al., which highlighted the importance of stringent glycemic management in improving wound healing rates in diabetic foot ulcers [23,24]. Our findings underscore the importance of achieving and maintaining optimal glycemic control in patients with DFUs to improve wound healing outcomes. Clinicians should prioritize comprehensive diabetes management, including lifestyle interventions and pharmacological treatments, to reduce HbA1c levels and enhance wound healing.

Limitations and Future Directions: While our study provides valuable insights, there are some limitations. The sample size was relatively small, and the study was conducted at a single center, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Future research should involve larger, multicenter studies to validate these findings and explore additional factors influencing wound healing outcomes, such as comorbid conditions and specific diabetes treatments.

Conclusion

This study highlights the critical association between glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels and wound healing outcomes in patients with diabetic foot ulcers. Our findings demonstrate that higher HbA1c levels are significantly linked to poorer wound healing, including larger baseline wound size, slower reduction in wound size, and delayed time to wound closure. These results emphasize the importance of stringent glycemic control in improving wound healing outcomes. Clinicians should focus on comprehensive diabetes management strategies to achieve optimal HbA1c levels and reduce the risk of complications.

Future research should explore additional factors influencing wound healing and assess interventions to enhance glycemic control and wound healing in diabetic patients.

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